

Formation Constants of Al(III), Cr(III) and Fe(III) Complexes with Some Substituted Salicylaldehydes

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Formation constants of complexes of salicylaldehydes and its derivatives with Al(III), Cr(III) and Fe(III) have been determined at 30° in dioxane-water (75% v/v) medium containing 0.1M NaClO₄ using Calvin-Bjerrum technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The relation between log K₁^H and log K has been investigated.

IN continuation of our earlier studies¹ on the determination of formation constants of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II) chelates with substituted salicylaldehydes, the formation constants of Al(III), Cr(III) and Fe(III) chelates with salicylaldehyde, 3-chloro, 4-hydroxy, 5-iodo, 6-chloro and 3-nitro-5-methyl substituted salicylaldehydes as well as with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde² have been determined. The data reported in this work are in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water medium at an ionic strength 0.1M (NaClO₄) and 30° ± 0.1°.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AR grade. Salicylaldehyde was obtained from Bush (Germany) and 4-hydroxysalicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde from B.D.H. (England). The details of preparations of remaining substituted salicylaldehydes, metal perchlorates and purification of dioxane are given in previous publication¹.

The procedure employed to carry out potentiometric titrations, the description of pH meter used, the calculations of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} , pK and log K values were the same as given in earlier communication.

Results and Discussion

For the chelates of substituted salicylaldehydes with Al(III), Cr(III) and Fe(III) ions, the highest value of \bar{n} is 2.6, thereby indicating conclusively the formation of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexes. From \bar{n} values, it was seen that in these systems 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 complexation occurs in short range of B(pH) values. The increase in \bar{n} values is continuous for Al(III) and Cr(III) complexes while in the case of Fe(III) complexes, it is surprisingly high. Precipitation was obtained at B = 5.2 for Al(III), and B = 5.8 for Cr(III) ions, while in the case of Fe(III) it occurred at B = 2.8 - 3.0.

The values of log K₁, log K₂ and log K₃ for these complexes are given in Table 1 along with the reported

TABLE-1 pK AND LOG K VALUES

Sl. No.	Ligand	pK	Al(III)			Cr(III)			Fe(III)		
			log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃
1.	Salicylaldehyde	10.15	9.26	9.05	8.76	9.95	8.03	7.58	10.63	10.15	10.12
2.	3-Chloro-salicylaldehyde	8.55	7.94	—	—	8.46	6.79	—	—	9.08	9.34
3.	4-Hydroxy salicylaldehyde	12.91 9.14	12.61	12.02	11.71	13.07	11.45	10.68	—	13.33	13.24
4.	5-Iodo-salicylaldehyde	8.98	8.77	8.27	8.18	9.14	7.68	7.08	9.49	9.62	9.20
5.	6-Chloro-salicylaldehyde	9.65	8.70	8.49	7.90	9.04	7.46	—	10.54	10.20	9.48
6.	3-Nitro-5-methyl salicylaldehyde	6.48	—	—	—	7.04	5.23	—	—	7.41	7.20
7.	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	6.77	8.56	8.05	6.92	8.70	7.20	—	—	9.57	7.85

values of pK of substituted salicylaldehydes¹. For Fe(III) complexes, the values of log K₃ were approximately evaluated due to non availability of more \bar{n} values in the expected range and even this made impossible the calculation of log K₁ values in most of the systems. The differences in the values of log K₁ and log K₂ and log K₃ are less than unity for Al(III) and Fe(III) complexes while in the case of Cr(III) complexes it is higher than one excepting for 5-iodo complexes. In general, the differences in the values of log K₁ and log K₂, and log K₂ and log K₃ are of such magnitude that it leads to infer that complexation 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 might be occurring simultaneously.

The increase in the values of stability constants with decrease in ionic radii was observed in the case of Cr(III) and Fe(III) complexes. However, the stability of Al(III) complexes is more than these complexes. Similar observations have been reported by Banks and Singh³ in relation to Al(III)-5 sulfosalicylate complexes.

Log K = apK + b relation :

The plot of log K₁ vs pK for Al(III) complexes is linear with unit slope value. The points relating to

5-iodo and 4-hydroxy salicylaldehyde are, however, not on the straight line which indicates extra π -bonding stabilization. Even plots of log K₂ and log K₃ vs pK are found linear with slope values 1.30 and 1.46 respectively.

The plots of log K₁ and log K₂ vs pK in relation to Cr(III) complexes are linear with slope values 1.63 and 0.85 respectively while in the case of Fe(III) complexes only plot of log K₂ vs pK is seen linear with slope value 0.98.

Fe(III) forms stronger complexes with substituted derivatives of salicylaldehyde than the complexes of Cr(III) and Al(III). This has been confirmed by the formation curves.

References

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